

THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON CONSUMERS' WESTERNIZATION, LIFESTYLE DIMENSIONS, AND MATERIALISM IN THE ARABIAN GULF: THE CASE OF KUWAIT

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RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- This study aims to:
 - Explore the **current social media engagement** level of Kuwaiti consumers.
 - **Examine the influence** of social media usage on lifestyle, westernization, and materialism among Kuwaiti consumers.

THE SIZE OF ARAB SOCIAL MEDIA USERS

- It is estimated that there are over 82 million Arab social media users.
- GCC consumers use social media extensively, which has transformed how they **connect, communicate, and shop**, especially among **younger generations**.
- Therefore, social media for the Gulf consumer is becoming not just an interaction tool; it is a lifestyle.

SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT

- Refers to how users **interact** with content on social media, including likes, comments, shares, and other behaviors that show audience participation and **degree of interest**.
- Increased customer engagement can lead to higher **brand awareness, website traffic, and ultimately, sales** for companies on social media (Amirrudin et al., 2024).

GLOBAL SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT

- 80% of consumers have purchased a product after seeing it recommended by an **influencer** (Wang et al., 2024).
- 65% of customers reported that a post's link directed them to a product they were **not initially interested in buying** (Dalimunthe et al. 2023).

GLOBAL SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT

- 59% of social media users make "**unplanned**" purchases on social media (Yang et al., 2024).
- **COVID pandemic** accelerated social media adoption on a global scale (Alhaimer, 2021)

SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT IN KUWAIT

- 95.9% of Kuwait's population is actively engaged in social media; therefore, these platforms **dominate daily life, shaping opinions, trends, values, and even purchasing decisions** (Almutawaa & AlWazzan, 2024).
- It has fueled a trend of **impulsive overbuying** in the GCC (Azazz & Elshaer, 2022).

SOCIAL MEDIA AND LIFESTYLE DIMENSIONS

- Activities, Interests, and Opinions (AIO) is a widely used approach to understanding lifestyle, focusing on **what consumers do, what they care about, and their beliefs** (Špindler et al., 2025).
- For this study, three variables will reflect the (AIO) of consumer lifestyle dimensions:
 - **Consumers' Impulsive Buying** (to reflect activities),
 - **Attention to Social Comparison** (to reflect interests),
 - **Satisfaction With Body Image** (to reflect opinions)

IMPULSIVE BUYING

- Defined as a consumer's **unplanned buying** behavior (Adelaar et al., 2003)
- Consumers buy impulsively when they experience a **sudden, often powerful, and persistent urge** to purchase a product **immediately** (Zhou & Wong, 2004).
- It is driven by high **emotional activation, low cognitive control, and largely reactive** consumer behavior.

IMPULSIVE BUYING AND SOCIAL MEDIA

- A substantial portion of social media users have made impulse purchases, which led to either **immediate gratification or later regret** (Nuseir, 2020).
- Al-Abdallah et al. (2021) conducted a comprehensive GCC study of 1257 respondents, in which social media engagement was found to **significantly influence the decision to buy luxury cars**.
- **Saudi women** are more impulsive in making unplanned purchases than men, due to influencers on social media (Hashem, 2021).

HYPOTHESIS ONE

- **H1: Social media engagement has a significant positive effect on consumers' impulsive buying online.**

SOCIAL COMPARISON AND SOCIAL MEDIA

- It is the act of evaluating oneself against others, often to **evaluate** one's abilities, opinions, or social standing (Suls & Wheeler, 2012).
- Social media provides a continuous stream of information about others, making it easier to engage in social comparison, **often unconsciously** (Burke et al., 2020).

SOCIAL COMPARISON AND SOCIAL MEDIA

- **low self-esteem** and disordered eating habits (Bonfanti et al., 2025).
- It creates a **skewed perception of reality** that makes others feel like they do not measure up to their peers (Strimbu & O'Connell, 2019; Zheng et al., 2020).
- This effect is amplified by **constant exposure to filtered, often unrealistic portrayals** of others' lives (Ruan et al., 2023).

SOCIAL COMPARISON AND SOCIAL MEDIA

- Omani users' **psychological distress** is linked to social media content combined with upward social comparison (Al Azri et al. 2025).
- Significant correlation between **increased anxiety and decreased well-being** with Instagram engagement.
- The adverse effects were more severe for those who had greater **tendencies for social comparison**.
- Anxiety levels were **higher among female participants**, and age analysis indicated that **vulnerability decreased** after the age of thirty.

HYPOTHESIS TWO

- **H2: Social media engagement significantly increases consumers' attention to online social comparison.**

SATISFACTION WITH BODY IMAGE

- A person's perception of their body's size, shape, and general appearance, as well as its function (Goswami et al. 2012).
- It is a **subjective perception** influenced by cultural and media messages and individual experiences (Lee et al. 2025).
- Positive body image is demonstrated through showing respect, acceptance, and appreciation for one's body (Yang et al. 2025).
- Negative body image is linked to discontent with self and to **emotional and cognitive responses** to that perception (Rodgers et al., 2023).

BODY IMAGE AND SOCIAL MEDIA

- **Young people** may develop a negative body image as a result of exposure to **unrealistic body ideals** promoted on social media (Bonfanti et al., 2025).
- There is a significant relationship between social media and **harmful practices** aimed at achieving the **ideal body image** among surveyed UAE respondents (AlKindi et al. 2021).

BODY IMAGE AND SOCIAL MEDIA

- Increased social media usage among Bahraini respondents was associated with the **obsession over physical body imperfections that are frequently invisible to others** (Buali et al. 2024).
- This obsession was also linked to **comparing one's body image to that of others on social media and making assumptions about other people based on their appearance.**

BODY IMAGE AND SOCIAL MEDIA

- Frequent social media use is associated with greater **body image dissatisfaction** among Omani respondents (Riyami et al. 2024)
- The majority who had a negative body image spent **six to ten hours a day** on social media.
- There is a significant correlation between high levels of body image dissatisfaction and **passive social media use**, defined as the passive consumption of content without active interaction.

HYPOTHESIS THREE

- **H3: Social media engagement has a significant adverse effect on consumers' satisfaction with her/his own body image.**

CONSUMER MATERIALISM

- The degree to which a person views possessions and their acquisition as a source of fulfillment and happiness (Flouri, 1999).
- It is a personal value system where material goods are seen as important for personal well-being and social status.
- Excessive materialism leads to lower life satisfaction, financial difficulties, and psychological distress (Semmler & Bobby, 2013).
- Excessive buying and consumption can contribute to a culture of materialism and waste (Lekavičienė et al., 2022).

SOCIAL MEDIA AND CONSUMER MATERIALISM

- Social media increases **materialistic values** and influences **conspicuous purchase** behaviour (Jameel et al., 2024) through exposure to ideal online content, and influencer marketing (Dávila & Casabayó, 2025).
- This effect is amplified by the **ease of online shopping** and the **constant exposure to advertising** on social media platforms (Pellegrino & Shannon, 2022).
- Even **passive consumption** of Social media can be positively correlated with materialistic values (Thi & Yoonjae, 2024).

SOCIAL MEDIA AND GCC CONSUMER MATERIALISM

- In the Arabian Gulf, social media is influencing attitudes towards **luxury goods and purchasing behaviours** (Alsalloum & Gainous, 2025). This influence creates a desire to **acquire status symbols** to project a particular image on social media (Hurley, 2019).
- Compared to American users, Arab social media users demonstrated **higher levels of materialism and social media usage** (Kamal et al. 2013).
- Due to increased peer competition on social media, UAE citizens reported substantially **higher levels of materialism** than non-natives (Arthur et al. 2017).
- In Saudi Arabia, Jameel et al. (2024) found that social media use is **positively correlated with compulsive shopping** behavior.

HYPOTHESIS FOUR

- **H4: Social media engagement has a significant positive effect on consumers' materialism.**

CONSUMER WESTERNIZATION

- It refers to the **adoption of Western culture** (including preferences, behaviours, and purchasing patterns) by individuals in non-Western societies.
- It is reflected in increased demand for Western **brands**, changes in **food habits**, and shifts in **lifestyle choices** (Sajib et al., 2016).

SOCIAL MEDIA AND WESTERNIZATION

- Social media makes it easier for Western cultural trends to spread quickly, weakening regional customs, languages, and identities (Balogun & Aruoture, 2024).

SOCIAL MEDIA AND GCC WESTERNIZATION

- Social media has significantly impacted the Arabian Gulf consumer, leading to both **westernization and social change**, particularly among **younger generations** (Rahman & Al-Azm, 2023).
- This impact is evident in **increased consumerism, shifts in social norms, and new forms of communication** (Pripoae-Șerbănescu & Mațoi, 2023).
- **English remains the dominant language** on their social media platforms. For instance, on Twitter, 88% of users in the UAE tweet in English, followed by 87% in Qatar, 81% in Bahrain, 78% in Kuwait, and 60% in both Oman and Saudi Arabia.

SOCIAL MEDIA AND GCC WESTERNIZATION

- Such exposure to Western cultural norms through social media can lead to a perceived **decline in traditional values**, particularly among **youth**, who may find themselves **caught between their cultural upbringing and the influences they encounter online**.
- Data from the Arab Youth Survey (Asda'a BCW, 2022) across 17 Arab countries indicates that **Arab youth view the Arabic language as less important than their parents do**, yet they are concerned about the **erosion of traditional values and culture**.
- Additionally, they report **difficulty in disconnecting from social media**, which remains a daily source of information (Asda'a BCW, 2022).

HYPOTHESIS FIVE

- **H5: Social media engagement has a significant positive effect on consumers' westernization.**

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- The research follows a quantitative approach, surveying a **convenience sample** of consumers in **Kuwait**.
- An online questionnaire was administered, resulting in the collection of **514 usable responses**.
- All research variables used a **Likert** scale format.
- **Parametric statistics** were used to analyze the collected data through **SPSS** software

CRONBACH ALPHA VALUES

Scale Name	Cronbach Alpha Value
Social media engagement	0.96
Impulsive buying	0.94
Social comparison	0.90
Satisfaction with body image	0.85
Materialism	0.95
Westernization	0.98

SOCIAL MEDIA INVOLVEMENT AMONGST KUWAITI CONSUMERS

- Social media involvement amongst Kuwaiti consumers is concentrated around a moderate value

Social Media Engagement	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very Weak	6	1.2	1.2	1.2
Weak	123	23.9	23.9	25.1
Moderate	262	51.0	51.0	76.1
Strong	109	21.2	21.2	97.3
Very Strong	14	2.7	2.7	100.0
Total	514	100.0	100.0	

HYPOTHESIS ONE

- Regression analysis revealed a statistically significant positive effect of social media engagement on consumers' online impulsive buying

R Square 0.600	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.679	.085		7.941	.000
Social Media Engagement	.775	.028	.774	27.686	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Impulsive Buying

HYPOTHESIS TWO

- Regression analysis revealed a statistically significant positive effect of social media engagement on consumers' attention to online social comparison

R Square 0.593	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.779	.084		9.288	.000
Social Media Engagement	.751	.027	.770	27.320	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Attention to Social Comparison

HYPOTHESIS THREE

- Regression analysis revealed a statistically significant adverse effect of social media engagement on consumers' satisfaction with their own body image

R Square 0.798	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.502	.057		96.037	.000
Social Media Engagement	-.845	.019	-.893	-45.018	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction with Body Image

HYPOTHESIS FOUR

- Regression analysis revealed a statistically significant positive effect of social media engagement on consumers' materialism

R Square 0.533	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.841	.095		8.830	.000
Social Media Engagement	.755	.031	.730	24.188	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Materialism

HYPOTHESIS FIVE

- Regression analysis also revealed a statistically significant positive effect of social media engagement on consumers' westernization,

R Square 0.647	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.360	.081		4.432	.000
Social Media Engagement	.815	.027	.805	30.665	.000

A. Dependent Variable: Westernization

COMPARATIVE EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA

- When comparing the individual effect of social media involvement on the study's dependent variables, we conclude that the most substantial effect is negatively associated with consumer satisfaction with one's own **body image (-0.893)**.
- Respectively, the positive impact is demonstrated on consumers' **westernization (0.805)**, **impulsive buying online (0.774)**, **attention to social comparison online (0.77)**, and finally on consumers' **materialism (0.730)**.

INTERRELATIONSHIPS AMONG DEPENDENT VARIABLES

- To investigate the interrelationships among dependent variables in light of social media involvement, partial correlations and bivariate Pearson correlations are used to compare results before and after controlling for social media involvement's effect on the remaining variables.

PARTIAL CORRELATION OF THE DEPENDENT VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Controlling for the effect of Social media engagement		Impulsive Buying Online	Social Comparison Online	Satisfaction with Body Image	Materialism	Westernization
Impulsive Buying Online	Correlation	1.000	.928	-.869	.430	.306
	Sig (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	df	0	511	511	511	511
Social Comparison Online	Correlation	.928	1.000	-.861	.431	.321
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	df	511	0	511	511	511
Satisfaction with Body Image	Correlation	-.869	-.861	1.000	-.448	-.333
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	df	511	511	0	511	511
Materialism	Correlation	.430	.431	-.448	1.000	.259
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	df	511	511	511	0	511
Westernization	Correlation	.306	.321	-.333	.259	1.000
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
	df	511	511	511	511	0

BIVARIATE PEARSON CORRELATION OF THE DEPENDENT VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

		Impulsive Buying Online	Social Comparison Online	Satisfaction with Body Image	Materialism	Westernization
Impulsive Buying Online	Correlation	1	.971	-.939	.752	.738
	Sig (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	514	514	514	514	514
Social Comparison Online	Correlation	.971	1	-.935	.750	.741
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	514	514	514	514	514
Satisfaction with Body Image	Correlation	-.939	-.935	1	-.790	-.808
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	514	514	514	514	514
Materialism	Correlation	.752	.750	-.790	1	.693
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	514	514	514	514	514
Westernization	Correlation	.738	.741	-.808	.693	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	514	514	514	514	514

INTERRELATIONSHIPS AMONG DEPENDENT VARIABLES

- When comparing the results of Partial versus Pearson correlation analyses of the interrelationships among all dependent variables, it is evident that consumers' social media involvement amplifies these interrelationships, whether positively or negatively.

FINAL DISCUSSION

- These findings are consistent with previous literature and with similar research conducted across different cultures.
- The findings of the current research shed light on the strength and significance of social media's impact on consumers' lifestyles, materialism, and westernization within the Arabian Gulf culture, particularly in Kuwait.
- In addition, the findings showed that social media involvement amplifies the interrelationships among the study's dependent variables, thereby enhancing the significance, magnitude, and importance of this effect on consumers' social and financial decisions.

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